

Title: The blockchain: the principal disruption in the financial services industry

Name: Eugenio Duarte

Affiliation: Universidad Internacional Iberoamericana (UNINI USA); Universidad Europea del Atlántico (Spain)

The objective of this research is to determine the impact that the blockchain technology will have on institutions, particularly in the industry financial sector. The Blockchain is a technology that allows multiple entities to share a common database in a decentralized and distributed way, without the need for intermediation, where the consensus for the management of information is automatically performed through mathematical algorithms.

The study describes the operation of the blockchain technology in its different categories: public, private and hybrid or consortium, indicating the advantages and disadvantages in each case. Concerning the public blockchain, we deepen in Bitcoin and Ethereum, both permissionless, decentralized, with hundreds of distributed nodes on the Internet where each holds a complete copy of the blockchain. Additionally, we study the hybrid blockchain, permissioned, partially decentralized, only accessible to a predetermined group.

For the development of this research, we consult specialized books, articles, reports, news, academic investigations and expert opinions, with the purpose of defining the relevant concepts, capabilities and benefits of the blockchain. Additionally, we analyze some use cases within the financial sector to determine which specific problems solve and which processes improve this technology.

The study concludes that, in certain scenarios, the blockchain technology is superior to a traditional distributed database because it provides more significant advantages in data processing, consistency, redundancy and information security, without the need for intermediation, eliminating from the equation the human factor of confidence. Due to regulatory and technical drawbacks faced by financial institutions, among the different categories of the blockchain, the permissioned hybrid model will be the preferred option in the short term in the industry.

Keywords: Blockchain, Bitcoin, Ethereum, Fintech

Biography:

Eugenio Duarte is the Senior Technical Analyst of the ecommerce platform at Aldo Group, Montreal. He has a bachelor's degree in Computer Systems Engineering, an accredited international Master of

Business Administration (MBA) from Europe and North America, and various IT certifications in technologies such as cloud computing, networking, security, wireless, voice over IP, and Linux.

He is the author of two books: 1) *Invierta y hágase Rico en la bolsa* (a beginner guide to stock investing); 2) *Blockchain: la última disrupción en el sector financiero* (a complete guide to Bitcoin and Blockchain technology).